

ISic3023

I.Sicily inscription 3023

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

graffiti

Material

natural rock

(cave)

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Leontini

Place of origin (modern)

Lentini

Provenance

Coste di Palagonia

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Lentini, Coste di Palagonia

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI332346

1. Νυμφόδωρος κεχαρισμένα [ν] ²ρiscis² ταριχ[ο]πώλας [έ]πύγιζε Δάμυλιν.
- 2.

Edition: PHI332347

1. Δάμυλις ἄ κεχαρισμένα Νυμφοδώρου γυνὰ [— — — —].
- 2.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645379

PHI 332346

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Bibliography

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 42.0850

Manganaro, G. 1992. Iscrizioni "rupestri" di Sicilia. In Gasperini, L.(eds.), *Rupes loquentes: atti del convegno internazionale di studio sulle iscrizioni rupestri di età romana in Italia. Roma - Bomarzo 13-15.X.1989*. Rome. pp. 447-501. At 492-497
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